

Importance of Values & Norms

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Introduction:

Social values are cultural standards that indicate the general goods deemed desirable for organized social life. They provide the ultimate meaning and legitimacy for social arrangements and social behavior. They are the abstract sentiments or ideas. An example of an important of such a values in social life can hardly be exaggerated. A social value differs from individual value. An individual value is enjoyed or sought by the individual values which a man seeks for himself. Even though these values are commonly shared they do not become social values. As distinct from individual values, a values contain a concern for others welfare. Social values are organized within the personality of the individual. They regulate his thinking and behaving. The process of socialization aims to include these values in his personality, the ethos or fundamental characteristics of any culture are reflection of its basic values. The difference in social values result in divergent social structures and patterns of expected behavior.

Norms incorporate value judgment, Secord and Buckman say “A norms is a slandered of behavioral shared by group members against which the validity of perceptions is judged and the appropriateness of felling and behavior is evaluated.” Members of a group exhibit certain regularities in their behavior. Have been explained in terms of social norms. Norms, in popular usage, means a standard. In sociology our

concern is with social norms. That is, norms accepted in a group. They represent. Standardized generalization” concerning expected modes of behavior. As standardized generalization they are concept which have been evaluated by the group and incorporate value judgment. Thus it may be said that norms are based on social values which are justified by moral standards be said that norms are based on social values which aesthetic judgment. A norms is a pattern setting limits on individual behavior. Sociologists are interested mainly in operative norms, that is, norms that are sanctioned, one is not punished socially for refusing to “turn the other cheek’ Norms in order to be effective must represent correctly the relations between real events. They must take into account the factual situation. A rule requiring all men to have two wives would be valueless if the sex ratio did not permit. Therefore. The normative system, since it is meant to achieve results in the factual world, should be related to the events in the real world. Moral values are attached to them. They are modal practices. They set out the normative order of the group. Norms are standards of group behavior. An essential characteristic of group life is that it is possessed of a set of values which regulate the behavior of individual members.

A Normally Norms are great importance to society:

A normless society is an impossibility. It is impossible to imagine a normless society, because without norms behavior would be unpredictable. The slandered of behavior contained in the norms give order to social relations. Interaction go smoothly if the individuals follow the group norms. The normative order makes the factual order of human society possible. If there were no normative order there could be on human society possible. If there were no normative order there could be no human society. Man needs a normative order to live in society because human organism is not sufficiently comprehensive or integrated to give automatic responses that are functionally adequate for society. Man is incapable of existing alone. His dependence on society is not derived from learned responses to meaningful stimuli. Hence his dependence on society is ultimately a dependence upon a normative order.

Norms give cohesion to Society:

We can hardly think of a human group apart from norms. A group without norms would be to use the words of Hobbes," Solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and shorts. "The human organism in order to maintain itself must live in a normatively regulated social system. The normative system gives to society a cohesion without which social life is not possible. Those groups which cannot fail to survive because of the lack of internal co-operation.

Norms Influence Individual's Attitudes:

Norms influence an individual's attitudes and his motives. They impinge directly upon a person's self-conception. They are special demands to act made by his group. They are much more stable. They have the power to silence any previously accepted abstract sentiments

which they may oppose. They take precedence over abstract sentiments. Becoming a member of a group implies forming attitude in relation to a group norms. The norms determine and guide his intuitive judgments of others and his intuitive judgments of himself, they are deeper than consciousness. Becoming a member of a group consists of internalizing the norms of the group. Through internalization they become a part of himself automatically expressed in his behavior.

Conformity of Norms:

Norms are not formed by all groups in relation to every kind of behavior and every possible situation. They are formed in matters of consequence to a particular situation. They are formed in matters of consequence to a particular group. What matter are of consequence to a group depends upon the main purposes and goals of the group depends upon the main purpose and goals of the group, the relationship of that group to other groups. And other condition in which it operates. Likewise, the scope of behavior regulated by norms varies considerably in different groups. For example, the norms of some groups may pertain chiefly to ethical matters, while the norms of other groups may cover a broader areas of life including dress, forms of entertainment, education and so on.

The violators of norms suffer the following kinds of sanctions:

1. Violators of norms suffer loss of prestige;
2. Violators are subjected to ridicule, fines, imprisonment.

By contrast, those who conform to norms enjoy the expected co-operation from others, maintain good prestige in the group and receive positive rewards such as praise, bonuses and promotions.

Three questions have been posed in regard to conformity of norms:

1. Why some behaviors and attitudes subjected to normative controls and others are not?
2. Why is much conformity to norms found in some groups than in others?
3. Why some members of a group conforms more closely to norms than others?

These three questions deals respectively with focus, extent and distribution of conformity to norms Secondly, the needs whose satisfaction is necessary for socio-emotional satisfaction also lead to the formation of norms. These needs are, for example, the needs for belonging acceptance and support. In the family norms arise to ensure fair treatment and to prohibit competition and aggression. Thus there are norms regarding the behavior of the children towards their parents, the relations of brothers and sisters, wife and husband, father and son.

It may also be referred that one's public behavior is compelled by norms to a greater extent than ones private behaviors or beliefs because while public acts are open to surveillance, private behavior is not. Where sanctions cannot be applied, norms generally do not arise.

Further in groups where satisfaction of social emotional needs is dominant or where the tasks themselves are enjoyable, conformity is likely to be high. Thus when the tasks to be performed are boring, fatiguing or dangerous, conformity will below, unless the costs of non-conformity are correspondingly high. In situations where sanctions for non –conformity are weak the level of conformity also may be low.

Regarding conformity to norms three more points may also be seen. Firstly a norms need not be carried out to influence behavior. It is a mistake to suppose that absolute fidelity to norms is essential to society. Complete adherence would not only be impossible in the case of many

norms but would be disadvantageous for the society. Of course it is a duty of an individual to conform to norms but in some particular situations a moderate rather than a maximum level of performance may be achieve what the society needs, secondly, some norms may set such a high level for desirable conduct that average behavior of members' could approach it only at exceptional levels. Many norms do not become internalized. Many of them do not even become habitual, and some of them are not even obeyed. Thirdly in modern differentiated groups the degree for conform of groups. Those various groups may have conflicting norms. Therefore, the degree of conformity to norms may be in part a function of the extent to which norms of the groups are congruous with them.

Conclusion:

1. The standards which regulate behavior have been termed social norms.
2. Norms are standards of group behavior.
3. The normative system, since it is meant to achieve result in the factual world, should be related to the events in the real world.
4. Norms influence individual's attitudes, norms influence an individual's attitudes and his motives.
5. Norms are not formed by all groups in relation to every kind of behavior and every possible situation.
6. A norms by definition implies a sense of obligation.
7. A normless society is an impossibility, Norms are great importance's to society.
8. There are norms regarding the behavior of the children towards their parents, the relations of brothers and sisters, wife and husband, father and son.
9. The normative order makes the factual order of human society possible. If there were no

normative order there could be no human society.

10. The Norms are blueprints for behavior setting limits within which individuals may seek alternative ways to achieve their goals.
11. The differences in social values result in divert social structure and pattern of expected behavior.

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